

DESIGN OF FILTER BANKS FOR DATA FUSION BY SPECTRUM SUBSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we investigate on the design of filter banks that allow to substitute part of the spectrum of one signal with that of another signal. One application of this technique is fusion of data collected by sensors having different resolutions, that is a typical problem encountered in remote sensing, when data from low-resolution multi-spectral sensors and high-resolution panchromatic sensors are to be merged, either to alleviate visual identification tasks, or to expedite automatic detection and recognition. The approach that is proposed here is based on the use of cosine-modulated uniform filter banks. We assume that the ratio of the sampling periods of the input data is not integer and show how to design the filter banks so that spectra from different signals can be integrated with minimum distortion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fusion of data sampled with different step sizes is often necessary in many applications. Data fusion techniques have been devised in order to integrate different information sources, expedite feature detection and extraction, enhance spatial resolution and/or contrast. In the field of remote sensing, the ever increasing availability of airborne and space-borne sensors imaging in a variety of ground scales and spectral bands makes multi-sensor data fusion a discipline which should be capable to provide solutions that are more and more general for a number of applicative cases [1]. As an example, images scanned by multi-spectral sensors having low ground resolution can be integrated with higher resolution observations, representing the same scene imaged by a different sensor. As a result, the low resolution data, sensed in a number of physical bands each having a specific significance, are *spatially* enhanced by adding the edges and structures contained in the high frequency components of the high resolution image.

The problem may be stated as a substitution of the low frequency interval of the high resolution image spectrum with the spectrum of the low resolution image. An approach based on non-uniform filter banks is considered in [2]; however, it needs pre/post-processing to accommodate for general ratios between the sampling periods of the signals. A Laplacian pyramid approach, i.e. without high-pass filter, was followed

to merge data imaged with fractional scale ratios [3]. Filter banks are used to reconstruct, at low resolution, only an interval of the spectrum of a wide-band signal [4]. This is accomplished by using an M_1 -channel analysis and an M_2 -channel synthesis filter banks, with $M_2 < M_1$.

In this paper, we combine analysis and synthesis filter banks having different number of channels, as in [4], with the aim, however, of increasing the resolution of one signal as well as combining its spectrum with that of another signal. The filter banks are designed for direct, i.e. without pre-/post-processing, merging of signals with ratio between their sampling periods given by any fraction. In the following, only one-dimensional signals will be concerned, even if the application to two-dimensional signals is straightforward by using separable filtering.

2 SAMPLING RATE CHANGE VIA FILTER BANKS

In this section, we will analyse the problem of changing the sampling rate of a signal by means of digital filter banks with minimum degradation of the portion of spectrum that must be reconstructed. Here, we generalize results presented in [5][6].

Suppose that the input signal is analysed by a uniform M -channel bank. The uniform synthesis bank has L channels, with $L \neq M$. Only $K \leq L$ sub-bands are selected and reconstructed by the synthesis bank. We will assume that the selected sub-bands are the lower-frequency ones. If $K < L$, then $L - K$ sub-bands are set to zero in the synthesis process, or equivalently, only the first K synthesis filters are utilized. Hence, the ratio between the input and output sampling rate is L/M and the value of K determines the extension of the reconstructed spectrum.

The different cases are described by examples. Consider a real signal having spectrum, at positive frequencies, limited to $[0, 0.5]$ Hz and sampled at 1 Hz. If the sampling rate of the signal must be increased by a factor $5/3$, without changing the spectrum of the signal between 0 and 0.5 Hz, then the system shown in Figure 1, with $M = K = 3$, $L = 5$, can be used. All filters are assumed to be ideal. On the other hand, if only the spectrum between 0 and 0.3 Hz must be extracted with an output sampling rate equal to 0.6 Hz, then the system shown in Figure 1, with $M = 5$, $L = K = 3$, can be

Figure 1: System for generic sampling rate alteration

used. If we retain only the first $K = 2$ sub-bands, then we obtain the spectrum of the signal in the interval $[0, 0.2] Hz$ reconstructed with a sampling rate equal to $0.6 Hz$.

Consider now a slightly more complex case, in which we would like to extract the spectrum in the interval $[0, 0.4] Hz$ and to reconstruct it with a final sampling rate equal to $14/15 Hz$. A system like that shown in Figure 1 must analyse the input into $M = 15$ sub-bands, retain $K = 12$ sub-bands, and reconstruct the output signal spectrum with $L = 14$.

In general, let the ratios between the width of the spectrum interval to be retained and the input and output sampling rates be expressed by k_1/M_1 and k_2/L_2 . Then the system in Figure 1 can be used with $M = M_1 k_2 / \gcd(k_1, k_2)$, $K = \text{lcm}(k_1, k_2)$, $L = L_2 \text{lcm}(k_1, k_2) / k_2$, where $\gcd$ and lcm denote greatest common divisor and least common multiple, respectively.

The aliasing components and spectrum images that are created by down-samplers and up-samplers must be cancelled, at least partially. At the same time, as low degradation as possible of the desired spectrum must be present in the output. The analysis of such distortions is given in [4]. Using cosine-modulated filter banks, however, simplifies the design problem, that is reduced to finding the prototypes of the PSR analysis and synthesis banks. Aliasing cancellation and spectrum minimum distortion impose constraints on the prototypes. No constraint, instead, is placed on the number K of channels that are retained before the synthesis stage, so that we will assume $L = K$. Moreover, the design of a system for partial spectrum reconstruction, like that shown in Figure 1 leads to an analysis and a synthesis prototype, the roles of which can be interchanged. This means that if a system is designed to change the sampling rate by a factor $L/M < 1$, then also the prototypes for a system that changes the sampling rate by a factor $M/L > 1$ will be available. Therefore, to describe the design method we will assume, as in [4], that $L/M < 1$.

3 FILTER BANKS DESIGN

Let $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$ be two real signals sampled with periods $T_{s1} = 1/f_{s1}$ and $T_{s2} = 1/f_{s2}$. Let also $X_1(f)$ and $X_2(f)$ be the Fourier Transform of $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$, having periods f_{s1} and f_{s2} , respectively. Suppose that $T_{s1}/T_{s2} = M_2/M_1 < 1$, where M_1 and M_2 are coprime integers. Our goal is to create a new real signal $\hat{x}(n)$, having sampling period T_{s1} and frequency content (at positive frequencies) equal to $X_2(f)$ in the interval $(0, f_{s2}/2)$ and equal to $X_1(f)$ in the interval $(f_{s2}/2, f_{s1}/2)$. The signal $\hat{x}(n)$ can be ob-

tained by using the system shown in Figure 2. The signals $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$ are split into M_1 and M_2 sub-bands, respectively. Then, the first M_2 sub-bands of $x_1(n)$ are discarded and substituted by the M_2 sub-bands of $x_2(n)$. The signal $\hat{x}(n)$ is obtained by synthesizing the new set of M_1 sub-bands. In this way, the low frequency content of $x_1(n)$ is substituted by the spectrum of $x_2(n)$. We will use cosine-modulated filter banks [7] built by using different prototypes. The analysis and synthesis filters are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_k(n) &= 2h(n) \cos \left[(2k+1) \frac{\pi}{2M_1} \left(n - \frac{N_H-1}{2} \right) + (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{4} \right], \\
 k &= 0, 1, \dots, M_1 - 1 \\
 g_k(n) &= 2g(n) \cos \left[(2k+1) \frac{\pi}{2M_2} \left(n - \frac{N_G-1}{2} \right) + (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{4} \right], \\
 k &= 0, 1, \dots, M_2 - 1 \\
 f_k(n) &= 2h(n) \cos \left[(2k+1) \frac{\pi}{2M_1} \left(n - \frac{N_H-1}{2} \right) - (-1)^k \frac{\pi}{4} \right], \\
 k &= 0, 1, \dots, M_1 - 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The prototypes $h(n)$ and $g(n)$ are linear phase, power-complementary [7] and have length N_H and N_G , respectively. The transfer functions of the filters are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_k(z) &= H(zW_{2M_1}^{-(k+0.5)}) b_k^H a_k^H \\
 &\quad + H(zW_{2M_1}^{k+0.5}) (b_k^H)^* (a_k^H)^* \\
 F_k(z) &= H(zW_{2M_1}^{-(k+0.5)}) b_k^H (a_k^H)^* \\
 &\quad + H(zW_{2M_1}^{k+0.5}) (b_k^H)^* a_k^H \\
 G_k(z) &= G(zW_{2M_2}^{-(k+0.5)}) b_k^G a_k^G + \\
 &\quad + G(zW_{2M_2}^{k+0.5}) (b_k^G)^* (a_k^G)^*
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

in which $W_M = e^{j2\pi/M}$, $a_k^H = b_k^G = e^{j\frac{\pi}{4}k}$, $b_k^H = e^{-j(2k+1)\frac{\pi}{2M_1}\frac{N_H-1}{2}}$, and $b_k^G = e^{-j(2k+1)\frac{\pi}{2M_2}\frac{N_G-1}{2}}$; the superscript $*$ denotes complex conjugation.

The sub-bands of $x_2(n)$ are obtained by filtering $x_2(n)$ with modulated versions of $g(n)$ and down-sampling by a factor M_2 . Then, they are up-sampled by a factor M_1 and filtered with modulated versions of $h(n)$. It is apparent that the prototypes $g(n)$ and $h(n)$ cannot be designed independently of each other in order to allow aliasing cancellation between adjacent channels. Aim of this work is showing how to jointly design $h(n)$ and $g(n)$. Aliasing components located in frequency at the transition between the two filter banks (around $\pi M_2/M_1$, in normalized frequency), however, do not cancel each other. The output signal can be written as

Figure 2: Spectrum substitution by using M_1 and M_2 -channel filter banks.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X}(z) &= \frac{1}{M_2} \sum_{k=0}^{M_2-1} F_k(z) \\ &\cdot \left(\sum_{l=0}^{M_2-1} X_2(z^{M_1/M_2} W_{M_2}^l) G_k(z^{M_1/M_2} W_{M_2}^l) \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{M_1} \sum_{k=M_2}^{M_1-1} F_k(z) \\ &\cdot \left(\sum_{l=0}^{M_1-1} X_1(z W_{M_1}^l) H_k(z W_{M_1}^l) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The component corresponding to $l = 0$ in the inner summations is the desired merged signal, whereas the terms with $l \neq 0$ are aliasing components, the effects of which must be minimized. For $l = 0$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{X}(z) &= X_2(z^{M_1/M_2}) \cdot \frac{1}{M_2} \sum_{k=0}^{M_2-1} G_k(z^{M_1/M_2}) F_k(z) \\ &+ X_1(z) \cdot \frac{1}{M_1} \sum_{k=M_2}^{M_1-1} H_k(z) F_k(z) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

As it can be seen, the merged signal is related to $x_2(n)$ at low frequencies (the frequency scaling factor M_1/M_2 in $X_2(z^{M_1/M_2})$ is due to the use of normalized frequencies) and to $x_1(n)$ at high frequencies. Since the transition bands of the filters are not ideal, perfect substitution of the spectra cannot occur and distortion around $\omega = M_2/M_1\pi$ is unavoidable. Elsewhere, however, spectrum distortion is negligible if

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{M_2} \sum_{k=0}^{M_2-1} G_k\left(\frac{M_1}{M_2}\omega\right) F_k(\omega) &= cz^{-\alpha\omega} \quad 0 \leq \omega < \frac{M_2}{M_1}\pi - \epsilon \\ \frac{1}{M_1} \sum_{k=M_2}^{M_1-1} H_k(\omega) F_k(\omega) &= cz^{-\alpha\omega} \quad \frac{M_2}{M_1}\pi + \epsilon < \omega \leq \pi \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where c and α are constants, and ϵ depends on the transition width of the prototypes. From the first expression in (5), it can be seen that acceptable spectrum reconstruction for the signal $x_2(n)$ is possible if constraints on the prototype $g(n)$ are imposed. Since linear phase prototypes are used, we have

$$\begin{aligned} H(\omega) &= H_{\mathcal{R}}(\omega) e^{-j\frac{N_H-1}{2}\omega} \\ G(\omega) &= G_{\mathcal{R}}(\omega) e^{-j\frac{N_G-1}{2}\omega} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $H_{\mathcal{R}}(\omega)$ and $G_{\mathcal{R}}(\omega)$ are real functions. By substituting (2) and (6) into (4), we can express the reconstructed signal as a function of the prototype frequency responses. After some manipulations, it can be demonstrated that Eq. (5) with $c = 1/M_1$ and $\alpha = N_H - 1$ holds if $h(n)$ is a power complementary prototype and the following constraints are imposed:

$$\frac{N_G - 1}{2} \cdot \frac{M_1}{M_2} = \frac{N_H - 1}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$G_{\mathcal{R}}(\omega) = \begin{cases} \frac{M_2}{M_1} H_{\mathcal{R}}\left(\frac{M_2}{M_1}\omega\right), & 0 \leq \omega < \pi/M_2 \\ 0, & \pi/M_2 \leq \omega \leq \pi \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

So far, we have considered the signal in the absence of the aliasing components. Consider the terms in (3) with $l \neq 0$. It is well-known that the main contribution to aliasing is given by the components that are located at the higher and lower edges of the pass-band of $F_k(\omega)$ [8]. These components are generated by filtering with $F_k(\omega)$ the sub-band replicas created in the adjacent channels by up-sampling. In Pseudo-QMF design the main components of aliasing in adjacent branches sum to zero, thus achieving Near Perfect Reconstruction. It can be shown that if (8) is fulfilled, then the main component of aliasing cancel each other, except for the components created around the frequency $\pi M_2/M_1$. In fact, the aliasing components at the upper edge of the passband of $F_{M_2-1}(\omega)$ and at the lower edge of the passband of $F_{M_2}(\omega)$, depend on different signals, that is on $X_2(\omega)$ and $X_1(\omega)$, respectively, and, therefore, do not cancel each other.

4 EXAMPLE OF SPECTRUM SUBSTITUTION

One example of spectrum substitution is now presented. We will assume that part of the spectrum of a signal must be substituted with part of the spectrum of a second signal. Synthetic signals are used to better highlight where substitution occurs. Consider two sequences $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$ having different spatial resolutions. In this example their length is 1152 and 768 samples, respectively, and we assume $T_{s1}/T_{s2} = 2/3$. Their spectra are shown in the upper and central part of Figure 3(a). We would like to substitute 1/2 of the spectrum of $x_1(n)$ with 3/4 of the spectrum of $x_2(n)$. Note that in Figure 3 all spectra are shown by using normalized frequency, so that the frequency interval where $X_2(\omega) \neq 0$ is approximately the same interval covered by the first half of the spectrum $X_1(\omega)$. In other words, we would like to substitute the semicircle shaped part of $X_1(\omega)$ with the triangle shaped part of $X_2(\omega)$. The system of Figure 2, with $M_1 = 6$ and $M_2 = 4$, can be used, but with the difference that only the first $K = 3$ subbands derived from $x_2(n)$ are substituted to the first K subbands derived from $x_1(n)$. The filter banks used in the analysis and synthesis stages are shown in Figure 3(b). The Pseudo-QMF prototype $h(n)$ has length $N_H = 37$ and was designed by using the method in [9]. The prototype $g(n)$ has length $N_G = 25$ and has been designed by frequency sampling of $H(\omega)$ according to (8). Figure 3(a) also shows the signal reconstructed after merging $x_1(n)$ and $x_2(n)$.

Figure 3: (a): Spectra of synthetic signals $x_1(n)$ (top) and $x_2(n)$ (middle), used for fusion of data sampled with $T_{s1}/T_{s2} = 2/3$, and merged signal (bottom). (b): Frequency responses of the analysis filters of six (top) and four (bottom) channel banks allowing fusion of data sampled with $T_{s1}/T_{s2} = 2/3$. In the example, only the first three subbands derived from $x_2(n)$ are substituted to the first three subbands derived from $x_1(n)$.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A new method to design filter banks that allow fusion of data having different resolution has been proposed. The application of this method to a specific case study, concerning Landsat TM (30 m) and MOMS-2P (18 m) images (3:5 scale ratio) is presently being investigated [10].

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